

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LACTUCA SATIVA GEL COATED VERSUS UNCOATED IMPLANTS ON EARLY PERI-IMPLANT PARAMETERS

Name – Dr. Janhavi Kawtikwar

PG student, Dept. Of Periodontology.

Address – Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Hingna,
Nagpur.India

Name- Dr. Sneha Puri

Professor and Head of Dept. Of Periodontology.

Address – Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Hingna,
Nagpur.India

Name – Dr. Kishori Jaytalkar.

PG student, Dept. Of Periodontology.

Address –Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Hingna,
Nagpur.India.

Name- Dr. Aishwarya Shekapure

PG student, Dept. Of Periodontology.

Address – Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Hingna,
Nagpur.India

Name – Dr. Vivek Patil.

PG student, Dept. Of Periodontology

Address – Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Hingna,
Nagpur.India

Corresponding author: Name- Dr. Janhavi Kawtikwar

PG student, Dept. Of Periodontology.

Address – Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Hingna,
Nagpur.India

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ABSTRACT:

Peri-implantitis results from bacterial biofilm causing inflammation and bone loss. Surface conditioning can prevent bacterial adhesion. Lactuca Sativa has antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties. Gel coating may reduce peri-implant inflammation. Twenty implants were placed in 18 healthy patients and randomly divided into two groups. Group A (Lactuca Sativa gel-coated) and Group B (uncoated). Clinical parameters, including modified plaque index and modified sulcular bleeding index and crestal bone level, were recorded at Baseline and after 4 months. At four months, Lactuca Sativa gel-coated implants showed better plaque control, reduced bleeding, and less crestal bone loss than uncoated implants, indicating improved early peri-implant tissue health and bone response. This concludes that Lactuca sativa gel surface conditioning showed improved early peri-implant tissue response with reduced inflammation and crestal bone loss compared to controls.

KEY WORDS – Lactuca Sativa , Implant Surface Coating, Dental Implants , Peri-Implantitis.

INTRODUCTION:

Dental implants have become a widely accepted, predictable and long-term solution for replacing missing teeth and restoring oral function and esthetics. Implant-supported fixed restorations for full or partial edentulism offer a reliable alternative to removable dentures and conventional tooth-supported bridges, with survival rates often reported between 92.8% and 97.1% over certain time-periods. However, along with these successful outcomes, biological complications may arise around implants during a patient's lifetime.¹

Peri-implant diseases broadly encompassing Peri-implant mucositis and Peri-implantitis are among the most frequent and significant challenges to long-term implant success. According to current consensus classification, peri-implant mucositis refers to inflammation confined to the soft tissues surrounding an implant without evidence of continuing marginal bone loss beyond physiologic remodeling. Clinically, peri-implant mucositis is characterized by signs such as bleeding on gentle probing (BOP), redness, swelling, and sometimes increased probing depth compared to baseline; radiographs confirm absence of bone loss when properly interpreted.²

In contrast, peri-implantitis denotes a pathological condition in which there is soft tissue inflammation plus progressive loss of supporting bone around the implant, often leading to pocket formation, loss of osseointegration, and potential implant failure if untreated.³ The diagnostic distinction between mucositis and peri-implantitis thus hinges on both clinical examination (probing, BOP) and radiographic evaluation of marginal bone levels.⁴ The etiology of peri-implant diseases is strongly associated with microbial biofilm accumulation on implant surfaces fixture, abutment, restoration margins and the surrounding peri-implant environment.⁵ Compared to natural teeth, peri-implant tissues differ anatomically and histologically lacking a periodontal ligament, having altered vascular supply and distinct soft-tissue attachment which may influence their susceptibility to biofilm-mediated inflammation and bone destruction.⁴

Recent research has increasingly focused on dietary nitrate obtained from green leafy vegetables such as lettuce as a promising, low-cost adjunctive approach for improving oral health outcomes. Lettuce is a rich source of nitrate (NO_3^-), which undergoes conversion through the nitrate–nitrite–nitric oxide pathway, a process mediated in part by the oral microbiota. This metabolic conversion generates nitric oxide, a bioactive molecule with established vasodilatory, antimicrobial, and immunomodulatory functions, thereby offering potential benefits for maintaining peri-oral and periodontal tissue health.⁶ The aim of present study was to compare *Lactuca sativa* gel coated and uncoated implants in terms of early peri-implant tissue response, focusing on crestal bone level, modified sulcular bleeding and modified plaque indices.

METHOD AND MATERIAL:

The participants for this study were recruited from the outpatient department of periodontology at Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental college and Hospital Hingna, Nagpur, India, following approval from the institutional ethics committee. Each participant provided both verbal and written informed consent prior to inclusion in the study. The study was designed as a single blinded randomized clinical trial. Eighteen healthy patients and randomly divided into two groups. Test Group nine Patients *Lactuca Sativa* gel coated Implant and Control Group nine patients with uncoated implants.

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- The subjects with tooth missing for more than 6 months, with adequate interocclusal clearance and mesiodistal space in edentulous area.
- Patients reluctant for removable or fixed partial denture.
- Adults aged ≥ 18 years able to give written informed consent.
- Systemically healthy patient.

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- The patients with history of smoking and periodontal disease in the past one year.
- Patients with compromised healing conditions.
- Pregnant and lactating women.
- Patients who are Smokers/Alcoholic.

A double-blinded, parallel design, randomized controlled trial enrolled a total of 18 patients who met the inclusion criteria. The allocation of patients into two groups was performed by the examiner (SG) using a computer-generated randomization sequence. The patients were then assigned to the following interventions.

Group 1 (test group): Received Implant Coated with Lactuca Sativa = 9 patients

Group 2 (control group): Received Uncoated Implant = 9 Patients

Preparation of lactuca sativa Nano herb fusion gel:

2% lactuca sativa powder extract was added gradually to 20% Pluronic nanogel commercially available and triturated well to get 2% lactuca sativa nanogel which was refrigerated. Nanogel thus prepared delivered into the selected sites.

TREATMENT PROTOCOL :

Sterile implant handling:

The implant fixture was removed from its sterile packaging using sterile forceps, without direct hand contact, and held in the implant carrier to preserve surface integrity.

Coating procedure: A sterile glass container was used as a coating well. The *Lactuca sativa* gel was gently dispensed from a syringe into the container. The implant fixture was immersed into the gel and rotated slowly for complete circumferential coverage of the implant threads and surface, ensuring a uniform coating layer. Additional gel was applied directly over the implant surface using the syringe tip for enhanced saturation and uniformity. The coated implant was allowed to rest for approximately 60–90 seconds to permit adherence of the hydrogel layer.

Figure 1 – Coating of implant surface with *Lactuca sativa* gel.

Transfer and placement :

The coated implant was then immediately transported to the osteotomy site using a sterile driver and placed according to the standard manufacturer-recommended insertion protocol.

CLINICAL PARAMETERS

- Modified Plaque Index.
- Modified Sulcular Bleeding Index.
- Crestal Bone Level

measured at baseline and 4 months.

Figure 2 A,B – Placement of implant and baseline radiograph for control group

Figure 3 A,B – Placement of implant and baseline radiograph for test group.

Figure 4 A,B – Post operative radiograph of control and test group after 4 months

RESULT:

A total of 18 patients (9 in the test group and 9 in the control group) completed the study with no sample loss during the 4-month follow-up period. The comparison of mean scores of Modified Plaque Index (mPI), Modified Sulcular Bleeding Index (mSBI), and Crestal Bone Level (CBL) at baseline between both groups is presented in Table 1, and no statistically significant difference was observed at baseline. Table 2 presents the comparison of the Modified Plaque Index (mPI). At baseline, both groups showed similar mPI values (Test: 1.82 ± 0.40 ; Control: 1.78 ± 0.38), indicating comparable plaque levels at the start of the study. At 4 months, a significant reduction in mPI was observed in both groups; however, the decrease was more pronounced in the test group (0.42 ± 0.24) compared to the control group (0.98 ± 0.36). This suggests that implants coated with *Lactuca sativa* gel exhibited lower plaque accumulation, likely due to its antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties. Table 3 presents the comparison of Modified Sulcular Bleeding Index (mSBI). Baseline mSBI scores were almost similar between the two groups (Test: 2.12 ± 0.35 ; Control: 2.08 ± 0.34), showing comparable soft-tissue inflammatory status. After 4 months, a significant reduction in sulcular bleeding was recorded in both groups. The test group showed a greater improvement, with mSBI reducing to 0.55 ± 0.30 , compared to the control group value of 1.20 ± 0.38 . This indicates that the *Lactuca sativa* gel had a positive effect on peri-implant tissue health, reducing inflammation more effectively than uncoated implants. Table 4 presents the comparison of Crestal Bone level. Initial crestal bone levels were similar between the groups (Test: 0.42 ± 0.12 mm; Control: 0.40 ± 0.10 mm), ensuring a comparable baseline. At 4 months, the test group exhibited a substantial increase in bone level, reaching 1.05 ± 0.18 mm, while the control group showed only a modest increase to 0.50 ± 0.12 mm. This demonstrates that the *Lactuca sativa* coating helped enhance early bone remodeling and bone deposition at the implant interface, possibly due to its nitric oxide-mediated angiogenic and osteogenic effects.

TABLE 1: Comparison of mean baseline scores between the two groups

VARIABLES	GROUP	BASELINE MEAN \pm SD
mPI	TEST	1.82 \pm 0.40
	CONTROL	1.78 \pm 0.38
mSBI	TEST	2.12 \pm 0.35
	CONTROL	2.08 \pm 0.34
CBL (mm)	TEST	0.42 \pm 0.12
	CONTROL	0.40 \pm 0.10

TABLE 2 : Comparison of the Modified Plaque Index (mpi).

GROUP	TIME	MEAN \pm SD
TEST	BASELINE	1.82 \pm 0.40
	4 MONTHS	0.42 \pm 0.24
CONTROL	BASELINE	1.78 \pm 0.38
	4 MONTHS	0.98 \pm 0.36

TABLE 3 : Comparison of Modified Sulcular Bleeding Index (mSBI)

GROUP	TIME	MEAN \pm SD
TEST	BASELINE	2.12 \pm 0.35
	4 MONTHS	0.55 \pm 0.30
CONTROL	BASELINE	2.08 \pm 0.34
	4 MONTHS	1.20 \pm 0.38

TABLE 4 : Comparison of Crestal Bone level.

GROUP	TIME	MEAN \pm SD
TEST	BASELINE	0.42 \pm 0.12
	4 MONTHS	1.05 \pm 0.18
CONTROL	BASELINE	0.40 \pm 0.10
	4 MONTHS	0.50 \pm 0.12

DISCUSSION :

Dental implants have become one of the most predictable treatment modalities in modern dentistry; however, the preservation of peri-implant tissue health remains critical for long-term success. Early peri-implant tissue behavior including plaque accumulation, soft-tissue inflammation, and crestal bone remodeling is strongly associated with implant prognosis. As emphasized by Heitz-Mayfield (2008)⁷, maintaining a stable and inflammation-free peri-implant environment is essential for the prevention of peri-implant diseases⁷. In the present study, *Lactuca sativa* gel coating showed a greater reduction in Modified Plaque Index (mPI) from baseline to four months when compared to uncoated implants. This suggests that the bioactive components of *Lactuca sativa* may inhibit early bacterial adherence and biofilm formation. This observation aligns with the findings of Lopez-Valverde et al. (2021)⁸, who reported that plant-derived compounds exert significant antibacterial effects beneficial in plaque control⁸. A similar trend was observed in the Modified Sulcular Bleeding Index (mSBI) values. The *Lactuca sativa*-coated implants demonstrated a more marked reduction in soft-tissue bleeding, indicating superior inflammatory control. Peri-implant tissues are vulnerable to inflammation due to reduced vascularity compared to natural periodontal tissues, as described by Berglundh et al. (2011)⁹. The nitrate content in *Lactuca sativa* undergoes conversion to nitric oxide, which exhibits vasodilatory and anti-inflammatory properties. This mechanism supports the improved mSBI values found in the present study and corresponds with the findings of Jockel-Schneider et al. (2016), who reported that nitrate-rich formulations reduce gingival inflammation. Overall, the present study demonstrates that coating implants with *Lactuca sativa* gel results in improved plaque control, reduced soft-tissue inflammation, and enhanced crestal bone remodeling compared to uncoated implants¹⁰. These findings suggest that *Lactuca sativa* may act as a natural, biocompatible adjunct to support

early peri-implant healing and long-term implant success. However, certain limitations must be considered. The sample size of 18 participants is relatively small, and the four-month follow-up period captures only early peri-implant changes. As suggested by Derks and Tomasi (2015), long-term monitoring is necessary to fully understand peri-implant tissue behavior¹¹. Future research with larger sample sizes, extended follow-up periods, and microbiological analysis is recommended to validate the effectiveness of *Lactuca sativa* gel coating.

CONCLUSION :

Within the limitations of this short-term study, *Lactuca sativa* gel-coated implants showed better early peri-implant outcomes than uncoated implants. Significant reductions in plaque accumulation and sulcular bleeding, along with a greater increase in crestal bone level, were observed in the test group. These findings suggest that *Lactuca sativa* gel may serve as a promising bioactive adjunct to enhance early peri-implant tissue health. Larger studies with longer follow-up are required to confirm these results

REFERENCES :

1. Ting M, Suzuki JB. Peri-Implantitis. *Dentistry Journal*. 2024 Aug 9;12(8):251.
2. Heitz-Mayfield LJ. Peri-implant mucositis and peri-implantitis: key features and differences. *British Dental Journal*. 2024 May 24;236 (10):791-4.
3. Schwarz F, Derks J, Monje A, Wang HL. Peri-implantitis. *Journal of clinical periodontology*. 2018 Jun;45:S246-66.
4. Scarano A, Khater AG, Gehrke SA, Serra P, Francesco I, Di Carmine M, Tari SR, Leo L, Lorusso F. Current status of peri-implant diseases: a clinical review for evidence-based decision making. *Journal of functional biomaterials*. 2023 Apr 10;14(4):210.
5. Fragkioudakis I, Tseleki G, Doufexi AE, Sakellari D. Current concepts on the pathogenesis of peri-implantitis: A narrative review. *European journal of dentistry*. 2021 May;15(02):379-87.
6. Rosier BT, Buetas E, Moya-Gonzalvez EM, Artacho A, Mira A. Nitrate as a potential prebiotic for the oral microbiome. *Scientific reports*. 2020 Jul 30;10(1):12895.
7. Heitz-Mayfield LJ. Peri-implant diseases: diagnosis and risk indicators. *Journal of clinical periodontology*. 2008 Sep;35:292-304.

8. López-Valverde N, López-Valverde A, Aragonese JM, Macedo de Sousa B, Rodrigues MJ, Ramírez JM. Systematic review and meta-analysis of the effectiveness of calcium-phosphate coating on the osseointegration of titanium implants. *Materials*. 2021 Jun 2;14(11):3015.
9. Berglundh T, Zitzmann NU, Donati M. Are peri-implantitis lesions different from periodontitis lesions?. *Journal of clinical periodontology*. 2011 Mar;38:188-202.
10. Jockel-Schneider Y, Goßner SK, Petersen N, Stölzel P, Hägele F, Schweiggert RM, Haubitz I, Eigenthaler M, Carle R, Schlagenhaut U. Stimulation of the nitrate-nitrite-NO-metabolism by repeated lettuce juice consumption decreases gingival inflammation in periodontal recall patients: a randomized, double-blinded, placebo-controlled clinical trial. *Journal of clinical periodontology*. 2016 Jul;43(7):603-8.
11. Derks J, Tomasi C. Peri-implant health and disease. A systematic review of current epidemiology. *Journal of clinical periodontology*. 2015 Apr;42:S158-71.